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SEMANTIC AND AUDIO-DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BRANDING, ADVERTISING AND PR-COMMUNICATIONS BASED ON AI TECHNOLOGIES

Tatiana Smolikova

doctoral student,

Belarusian State University of Culture and Arts culture and arts

Abstract

The article presents a historical retrospective of AI-technologies development. The theoretical approaches of research into the definition of the concept of 'artificial intelligence' are disclosed. The possibilities of using semantic experience in optimising text and visual content and using audio-dynamic elements to enhance the emotional impact on the audience are considered. The importance of co-creation on the basis of AI-technologies in creating effective forms of communications and their implementation in branding, advertising and PR-strategies, as well as the effectiveness of using new creative opportunities in creating personalised content on the basis of prompt-engineering has been determined

Keywords: artificial intelligence, AI-technology, prompt, prompt-engineering, branding, advertising communication, PR communication, semantic and audio-dynamic features

Introduction

The use of AI-technologies in various types of communications is becoming an integral part of the development and positioning of organisations' activities in the competitive market. Joint creativity of artificial intelligence (hereinafter - AI) and a human being allows to create unique content (tests, images, audio-video products) for specific brand objectives. Today, more than 60% of PR-specialists and more than 70% of marketers already use AI-technologies in their work [1], not only automating communication processes, but also helping to analyse and adjust marketing strategies of companies. This contributes to the development of interactive projects with the use of VR/AR technologies based on AI and the formation of immersive experience of brand activity positioning. This synergy of creativity - human and machine - allows us to better understand the evolutionary path of AI-technologies development and their impact on various types of communications, to apply diachronic, synchronic and comparative-historical research methods in the stated topic.

The aim of the article is to identify scientific approaches to the study of the concept of 'artificial intelligence', as well as to analyse the evolution of AI-technologies, their semantic and audio-dynamic characteristics in the implementation of communication strategies.

The study aims to identify the patterns that determine the impact of technological innovations on cultural practices and artistic expressions.

The evolutionary path of AI technologies

Looking at AI through the prism of scientific and cultural studies, one can find that the concepts of creating 'thinking machines' capable of logical reasoning and intellectual activity have deep historical roots. One of the earliest examples of such ideas is the work 'Ars magna' by the Spanish thinker and monarch Raymond Lullius (1235-1315), dating back to the 13th century [2, p.6].

This treatise, which raised questions about the possibility of mechanisation of thought processes, had

a significant impact not only on Lullius's contemporaries, but also on subsequent generations of scientists and philosophers and the Renaissance. Thus, the origins of modern AI concepts can be traced back to medieval philosophical and scientific enquiry, emphasising the long evolution of ideas in this field.

In 1837, Charles Babbage's Analytical Machine described the idea of a stored programme based on punched cards borrowed from Jacquard's loom. The instructions contained not only the operation code and operand number, like all programming languages, but also branching and loops [3, p. 23]. Babbage's machine was not tested in practice, but his idea led to software development, which was realised by Ada Byron. She wrote a programme for the analytical machine of Ch. Babbage and suggested the possibility of creating AI, later coming to the conclusion that the analytical machine 'cannot generate something new' [3, p. 24].

The electrical properties of the brain were proven as early as 1849 by the German physiologist E. Dubois-Reymond, and in 1875 by the English physiologist R. Caton. The scientists concluded that the brain is an electrical device.

The argument about thinking machines, started in different epochs (early Middle Ages and Enlightenment), continued in the XX century - the time of cybernetics and astronautics, inventions of electronic computing machines, information processing machines.

AI philosophy appeared in the early 20th century under the influence of the psychological science of behaviourism, whose representatives argued that the brain includes reflex mechanisms, and in order to induce an animal to a certain type of behaviour, it is necessary to use methods of encouragement and punishment [4, p. 24].

Despite the fact that this direction was not developed, research in AI theory continued. Thus, in 1936, the English mathematician and cryptographer Alan Turing described the concept of an abstract computing machine known as a 'Turing machine'. This device, consisting of an infinitely long ribbon divided

into cells with the numbers 0 or 1, could execute a limited set of commands. Later, by December 1943, A. Turing designed and built the first ever electronic computer, the Cosmos computer. Although this device was not designed for practical use, it allowed him to define a number of problems solvable by machine computation. In 1950, he published the article 'Computing Machines and the Mind' [5], where he formulated this ambitious goal, laying the foundation for further research in the field of AI.

Thanks to the works of A. Turing, the Hungarian-American mathematician and educator John von Neumann formulated the key computer principles that would form the basis of modern computer systems endowed with memory, analytics and data exchange. It was J. Neumann who would describe the relationship between the computer and the brain in his manuscript in 1956, where he would specify the exact mechanisms of information processing in the nervous system, which would prove accurate given the 'primitive' state of neuroscience for that time [6, p. 29].

The very term 'artificial intelligence' was proposed at a scientific seminar with a similar name at Dartmouth College (USA) in 1956. [7, c. 16]. At the same time, in 1957, an attempt was made to develop a system (perceptron) by researcher F. Rosenblatt, which is able to imitate the work of the human eye with the brain.

The interest of the scientific community and the number of studies on AI is confirmed by the sharp dynamics of the number of publications on neurocomputing since the late 1980s. Neural networks as technologies in AI implementation have become a key tool for solving a wide range of tasks, from image recognition and natural language processing to content generation and decision making in complex systems.

Today AI is associated with the concept of 'prompt engineering', perceived as a field that studies the skills of preparing, creating and optimising prompts (prompts) for neural networks, where a prompt is input data that the user gives to the AI model to get the desired answer [8, p. 22].

The concept of 'prompt' (from English prompt (noun), induce, inspire (gl.)). [9, p. 298] in the context of AI and natural language processing is a textual request or instruction that directs the generation of content by an AI system.

AI-technologies are successfully implemented in communications: branding, advertising and public relations. Semantic and audio dynamic techniques are particularly relevant to creativity, they aim to optimise communication tasks by personalising content, automating processes and improving audience interaction.

AI-technologies in branding, advertising and PR-communications: semantic and audio-dynamic creative techniques

Creative possibilities of branding, advertising and PR-communications based on AI-technologies allow to introduce various semantic and audio-dynamic elements, objects and characters that can find an unexpected solution in images based on prompt engineering. Features of neural networks to generate

unique artistic images and elements in branding, can help to implement any creative ideas, rebranding, if necessary, to update from a technical point of view the style of the organisation. Interesting solutions of co-creation can attract more attention of potential users, strengthen the emotional connection with the brand, emphasise and individualise the image style of the organisation and specify more precisely its values and mission.

Branding is a strategic process of creating a unique image and identity for an organisation that helps it stand out from its competitors and be easily recognisable to consumers. A good brand helps to establish trust with consumers, which in turn can increase loyalty to a product or company. It includes such elements as naming, mission, slogan, visual and audio identity, which together form the brand image [10, p. 67].

Also, branding can be defined as the process of creating a unique image that will reflect the values of the organisation. It is not only visual identity, but also the concept, emotions and associations that are associated with the activity of organisation in the minds of the audience [11].

The semantic characteristics of a brand based on AI technologies represent important aspects that help to shape its perception and identity.

Firstly, AI technologies enable the creation of personalised content by analysing consumer behaviour and preferences. This gives brands the ability to develop advertising messages and content that become more relevant and relevant to each customer, enabling deeper connections with audiences.

In addition, neural networks are able to process large amounts of data, revealing hidden patterns and trends in consumer behaviour, which helps to predict market demands and adapt them to specific offers in a timely manner, to design appeals in a variety of semantic and audio-dynamic forms of advertising.

AI technologies can also be used to create unique content, colour style and brand image. This includes the creation of slogans and texts, images, jingles or music radio spots for advertising and PR communication.

Emotional communication with consumers is also becoming more innovative thanks to AI capabilities. By analysing emotional and psychological reactions to various branding elements, the right content can be created to reinforce positive emotions. This promotes interaction with the brand and makes it more memorable [12, p. 26].

Automation of communications is another aspect that greatly improves customer interaction. With the help of chatbots and AI-based voice interfaces, an organisation can provide instant answers to user queries, which makes it possible to assess quantitative and qualitative indicators of work with customers and the level of their interest.

Finally, AI technologies allow for more accurate segmentation of the target audience. Analysing data on user behaviour allows you to adapt your marketing strategies to different brand segments, increasing the effectiveness of communications.

Thus, semantic brand characteristics based on AI-technologies not only help to position themselves in the

market, but also contribute to building long-term relationships with customers based on a deeper consideration of their image and preferences.

Audio dynamic branding features include the use of audio elements such as jingles or branded sounds. These elements help create an emotional connection with the consumer and increase brand memorability. For example, successful advertising campaigns often use music snippets or sound effects that become associative triggers for consumers.

Advertising communication implies [13]:

- a message encoded in text, sound and colour, which is addressed to a potential buyer of a product or service, as well as a response to it;
- a process of information transfer, which not only familiarises consumers with various goods, but also contributes to the formation of social stereotypes, values and standards;
- a tool that contributes to socio-cultural transformations.

PR-communication implies a system of managing interactions between an organisation and its public in order to create and maintain harmonious, open, equitable, mutually beneficial, trusting relationships and to form a positive image of the organisation [14, p. 18].

The main task of PR is to effectively communicate information about the organisation's activities, values and products, as well as to respond to public opinions and events that affect the reputation.

PR includes a wide range of actions, including the occasion to create information, interact with the media, organize events and engage in dialogue with various interests. It not only helps to create a positive image of the company, but also helps to resolve crisis situations, attract slowdowns and preserve relationships with customers and partners. Thus, PR-communication is a prerequisite for achieving strategic goals and increasing its competitiveness in the market [14, p. 3].

AI-technologies are able to endow advertising and PR-communications with semantic and audio-dynamic characteristics and provide higher speed and efficiency of personalised content creation, allowing brands to better interact with the target audience, adapting to its preferences in real time.

The main aspects of *semantic characterisation* include:

- Semantic richness : advertising texts should be clear and understandable to convey the benefits of a product or service to the consumer. Effective semantics helps to create associations with denotations of feelings and life situations, which helps to establish an emotional connection with the consumer [15].

- Use of signs and symbols: advertising and PR communications utilise a variety of sign systems including images, sounds and text. These elements must harmonise with each other to create a coherent image. For example, visual images can increase the meaning in words, enhance deeper perception [16].

- Social context refers to how advertising and PR materials are perceived and interpreted within a given social environment and cultural norms. This idea influences social factors on the content and form of

communication and how audiences respond to advertising messages.

- Adaptation to external conditions: knowledge of interests and external constraints allows advertisers and PR specialists to select the words and images that will resonate most with consumers. This increases the effectiveness of communications and promotes better perception of information.

Audio-dynamic characteristics are related to the use of sound elements in advertising and PR communications. They include:

- Sound effects and music that significantly increase the impact on the consumer, create the necessary mood and evoke associations with the product or brand.

- Voice Assistants: the use of AI technologies in generating voice assistants are becoming increasingly popular in advertising and PR communications. They can interact with users in natural language, providing information about products or services, making communication more interactive and personalised.

- Audio tools: creating vibrant audio identifiers (e.g. jingles) helps organisations create a unique image and increase brand awareness. Audio dynamic elements become part of a company's image and ensure brand memorability.

Therefore, semantic and audio-dynamic characteristics are essential tools in the arsenal of modern advertising and PR trends. Their proper use allows not only to effectively convey information to consumers, but also to create an emotional connection with them, which in turn ensures brand loyalty.

Conclusions

The evolution of AI technologies has come a long way from the first concepts of artificial intelligence to modern neural networks and deep learning. This process is characterised by the continuous improvement of algorithms and the expansion of AI applications - from image recognition and natural language processing to content generation and decision-making in complex systems.

Communication automation represents a crucial aspect that significantly optimises customer interactions. Using AI-powered chatbots and voice interfaces, an organisation can provide prompt reports to user queries, ensuring that a positive user experience is created and brand loyalty is increased.

The use of semantic and audio dynamic characteristics in branding, advertising and PR communications based on AI-technology, opens up new creative opportunities to create personalised content, which ultimately increases the effectiveness of marketing strategies. Prompt-engineering tools allow to accompany author's creative solutions in the creation of effective communications and elements of positioning the image of the organisation. Thus, the evolution of AI-technologies demonstrates not only the potential of modern communications, but also expands semantic and audio-dynamic techniques of creativity based on prompt-engineering, creating associative triggers for consumers.

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